

Literature Reloaded:

using databases to explore literary trends

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Researching genre literature

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- Existing research on genre perception relies on stereotypes and 'common knowledge'
- Reports on genre popularity rely almost exclusively on sales data
- **No clear definitions:** genres are fuzzy sets, easy to recognise at the centre but vague near the edge
- **No standard labelling:** publishers use broad categories

Speculative fiction

“Works presenting modes of being that contrast with their audiences’ understanding of reality, [with] key emphasis on speculative representation of what would happen had the actual chain of events or the matrix of reality-conditions been replaced with other conditions.”

- Gill 2013

Cambridge English Corpus

- A multi-billion word collection of written, spoken and learner texts compiled by Cambridge University Press.
- Primarily used in-house to inform English Language Teaching department and publications.
- Access is restricted to researchers working for Cambridge University Press and Cambridge English Language Assessment.

Cambridge English Corpus

Tools:

- **Word sketch difference** (how words differ in their context and behaviour)
- **'Thesaurus'** (words used in similar context)
- **Word sketch** (important co-occurring words)

Cambridge English Corpus

Problems:

- Number of entries falls sharply after 2008
- Small sample size

Nielsen BookScan

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- A commercial service aimed at publishing houses that gathers weekly sales figures from various UK booksellers
- Their statistics capture over 90% of British print book market
- Access is restricted to institutions who are Nielsen BookScan subscribers

Problems:

- Only rudimentary ebook and self-published market tracking
- Tracking by ISBN - bestseller charts do not always reflect actual bestselling titles
- Broad genre categories

Goodreads

goodreads

- The world's largest site for readers and book recommendations
- Over 30 million members
- Over 900 million books
- Users can categorise books with no pre-set labels or category names

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- Tracking popularity without having to rely exclusively on book sales data
 - Tracking perception of genre through user-created labels
 - Combined with Nielsen data: an insight into popularity of genres and discrepancies in use of genre labels

Sources

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Thank you!